

Highlights

Predictive control strategies for solar furnace systems on the basis of practical constrained solutions

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- Comprehensive study of four control strategies for solar furnaces is conducted.
- Model validation and linear model parameter analysis are performed.
- Practical NMPC balances performance and computational cost to enhance thermal stress trials.
- Real-world tests validate the selected PNMPC in meeting high-criteria requirements.

Predictive control strategies for solar furnace systems on the basis of practical constrained solutions

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Nonlinear predictive control
Model predictive control
Nonlinear control
Solar furnace
Solar energy

ABSTRACT

Controlling solar furnace systems presents significant challenges due to their nonlinear dynamics and uncertainties in model parameters. Therefore, this paper provides a comprehensive study of four predictive control strategies specifically tailored for solar furnaces: linear generalized predictive control (GPC), nonlinear GPC (NGPC), nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC), and practical NMPC (PNMPC). The primary objective is to address practical issues in solar furnaces, including nonlinear behavior, measured and unmeasured disturbances, and optimal control actions to enhance control performance and reliability in thermal resistance trials. Using real data from an actual solar furnace facility, the control strategies are evaluated in a simulation environment, considering various aspects such as control performance, computational burden, and robustness. Among the strategies, PNMPC proves to be the most promising, attending a compromise between control performance and computational cost. It exhibits a small error-index and significantly shorter processing time (20 times less) compared to NMPC in the simulated test. Consequently, PNMPC is implemented in the existing solar furnace SF60 in Plataforma Solar de Almería, Spain. Real-world results demonstrate the effectiveness of PNMPC in controlling the sample temperature during thermal stress trials in the solar furnace. The controller successfully handles system constraints and performs exceptionally with no steady-state error. As a result, the research outcomes provide suitable solutions to meet high-criteria requirements in thermal stress experiments in solar furnace systems. Furthermore, this study's findings advance the control engineering field in solar furnace systems, facilitating the transition toward sustainable and efficient use of solar energy.

1. Introduction

The paramount importance of solar energy extends beyond its role in power generation alone [1, 2, 3]. It also serves as a valuable resource for conducting material resistance experiments, particularly in thermal stress tests [4, 5, 6, 7]. By harnessing solar energy for such applications, it is possible to acquire valuable insights into the durability and performance of various materials, thus facilitating advancements in numerous industries.

In this panorama, solar furnaces play a crucial role in harnessing the sun's energy to perform material thermal resistance trials. The main functioning of solar furnaces is based on the sun-tracking collectors called heliostats that reflect solar irradiance towards a static parabolic collector, which concentrates a large amount of solar energy at its focal point, where the material sample to be tested is located. The amount of energy is regulated by opening a shutter between the reflector and the heliostat. Typically, these systems are operated manually, considering various temperature test profiles, sample materials, and environmental conditions, in which the experiment's success highly depends on the operator's skill during the test. As a result, the influence of human factors in controlling the solar furnace systems must be assertive to achieving superior criteria since unpredicted

disturbances and the system's nonlinear behavior make these requirements very difficult to achieve manually, and thus, high-specialist operators are required for this task. Considering this matter, control engineering poses a promising role in this field since automatic control strategies can enhance efficiency and trustworthiness in solar-powered systems [8, 9, 10].

In the last 20 years, there has been slow progress in the field of applied control engineering for solar furnaces. In general, the control strategies applied in solar furnaces focus on classical Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controls. For instance, the pioneering research of Berenguel et al. [11] has introduced automatic control studies for solar furnaces, including model formulations based on first principle equations and several PID controller schemes based on feedforward (FF) compensation, self-tuning control, anti-windup mechanism, and actuator constraint handling. Subsequently, in [12], a fuzzy controller has been evaluated for the process of copper sintering in a solar furnace. Later, an adaptive temperature control strategy is presented for solar furnace systems in [13] and in [14], in which the strategy is based on the exact feedback linearization associated with PI and FF strategies. In [15], the authors investigated in a simulation environment a control architecture in a cascade scheme to deal with the solar furnace nonlinearities in the shutter aperture and the sample temperature aiming for stability analysis through the Lyapunov functions. In addition, a generalized isodamping technique solution is presented by [16] in a robust PID controller to deal with the system nonlinearities

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and guarantee an acceptable performance regardless of the operating point.

The work developed in [17] presents an optimal control strategy on solar furnaces based on model discretization for the numerical integration of the nonlinear differential equations, with a drawback to consider specific tuning of the weigh tuning and prediction horizon to solve reference tracking error and high computational burden.

In the subsequent years, Model-based Predictive Control (MPC) strategies have also been considered to control solar furnaces. For instance, in [18], a Multistep Multivariable Adaptive Regulator (MUSMAR) in parallel with the PI controller is developed in order to deal with the nonlinearities of the solar furnace model. In [19], the authors have proposed two solutions have been proposed, first, a modified nonlinear Generalized Predictive Controller (NGPC), in which the free response is calculated using the nonlinear model while the forced response is used as the linearized model, and a switching control scheme that alternates between a constrained nonlinear control scheme and a PI controller. Moreover, still regarding addressing the system nonlinear dynamic issue, the feedback linearization technique with two-degree-of-freedom is presented in [20] and later is employed with a linear GPC in [21]. Also, in [22], a linear MPC with integral action is presented, in which the incremental form of the sample temperature variable is used, with the focus on avoiding the use of online adaptation mechanisms to overcome the changes in the system dynamics due to its nonlinear behavior. Lately, in [23], two control approaches have been studied for active cooling solar furnaces, namely, exact linearization and MPC with integral action, aiming to improve temperature reference tracking and increase the performance and operation of solar furnaces.

Aiming to resume the solutions of automatic control in solar furnaces, Table 1 categorizes the contributions in the literature regarding the types of control strategies applied in this system. As observed, most control strategies are employed to tackle the challenges associated with enhancing reference tracking performance, considering both the nonlinear characteristics of the system and its inherent constraints, encompassing a range of approaches, including linearization methods and adaptive solutions coupled with linear controllers. These aspects are highly related to control performance in practical scenarios. Firstly, the nonlinear dynamics of the system are multi-characterized due to the intensity of the thermal radiation in terms of the sample temperature to the fourth power, the shutter opening in terms of cosine functions, and the product of input and irradiance. Moreover, the different types of experiments require stringent control performance, subject to prescribed bounds on both the input and output variables, particularly for the sample temperature derivative. Therefore, controlling the sample temperature in solar furnaces is challenging for the control engineering field.

On the basis of the previous review and aiming to provide a further investigation of nonlinear controllers for solar furnace systems, this work presents the study of constrained

NMPC for solar furnaces considering disturbances compensation. The main objective is to propose a control solution based on optimal actions to acquire high performance in tracking and regulating the sample temperature in thermal resistance trials in solar furnaces, considering the restrictions in the maximum and minimum limits of input and output gradient thresholds. The focus of this work is grounded in the study and comparison of four different MPC strategies, namely, linear GPC, nonlinear GPC (NGPC, using the nonlinear model to calculate the free response), an explicit NMPC, and a Practical NMPC (PNMPC) [24], in which all controllers are formulated considering the irradiance and ambient temperature models to enhance disturbance compensations. To achieve the mentioned objective, an actual solar furnace located in the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), southern Spain, is used as the studied system. The methodology of this work follows the subsequent steps:

- First, the system model is investigated since it is the crucial aspect of the model-based controllers. In this stage, modeling calibration and validation are performed using actual open-loop data of the solar furnace SF60 of the PSA [5]. In addition, a linear model parameter analysis is conducted for a better understanding of the model behavior in different operating conditions.
- Secondly, all the proposed control strategies are evaluated in a simulation environment using actual data of the facility, comparing the controllers' performance, computational costs, and robustness regarding mismatch models.
- Finally, after evaluating the best compromise of the presented criteria, the best strategy is implemented in the actual system for different scenarios trials.

This work offers two significant contributions. Firstly, it provides a comprehensive comparison of four MPC strategies (GPC, NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC), specifically tailored to address practical aspects of solar furnace systems. This comparison encompasses various factors, such as disturbance compensation, constraints, and scenarios involving model mismatches. By thoroughly evaluating these strategies, valuable insights can be obtained regarding their suitability and effectiveness in real-world solar furnace applications. Secondly, this work introduces a novel control solution based on a nonlinear predictive controller for solar furnaces. This particular controller is designed to meet the stringent requirements of high-performance applications, offering a level of control that has not yet been explored or presented in the existing literature. By presenting this innovative control solution, this research aims to push the boundaries of control engineering in the context of solar furnace systems, opening up new possibilities for achieving exceptional performance levels. Moreover, this work is an extension of the results achieved in [25], presenting herein a larger and more comprehensive analysis of different predictive strategies with disturbance compensation for solar furnace systems.

Table 1

Controllers applied to solar furnace systems. Acronyms: PID - PID-based controllers, GS - Gain Scheduling, FF - FeedForward action, AC - Adaptive Controller, OC - Optimal Controller, RC - Robust Controller, FC - Fuzzy Controller, FBL - FeedBack Linearization strategies, MPC - Model-based Predictive Controller, NMPC - Nonlinear MPC. FBL strategies are considered those that use the inversion of the model to calculate the control action. FF action is considered as an external block scheme. *In [19], the NMPC is not considered entirely since, for one approach, only a part of the system prediction is based on the nonlinear model, and for the second approach, a switching scheme is employed for the nonlinear controller and PI control.

References	Controller									
	PID	GS	FF	AC	OC	RC	FC	FBL	MPC	NMPC
[11]	X		X	X						
[12]							X			
[13]	X			X				X		
[14]				X				X		
[15]	X			X				X		
[16]	X	X				X				
[17]					X					
[18]	X			X					X	
[19]	X			X				X	X	/*
[20]	X							X		
[21]								X	X	
[22]									X	
[23]								X	X	

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reports the system description and modeling validation/calibration experiments conducted in the SF60. Moreover, a linear model parameter analysis is performed regarding the system operating points. In Section 3, the four predictive controllers are proposed, and simulation comparisons are carried out to study control performance and computational costs. Section 4 depicts the results of the nonlinear controller PNMPC applied in the real facility. Finally, in Section 5, the main conclusions of this work are reported.

2. Solar furnace model study

In this section, the SF60 solar furnace located in PSA is studied to acquire its validated model. Herein, a nonlinear first principle model is used to describe the dynamic evolution of the sample temperature as a function of the solar irradiance, the shutter aperture, and the ambient temperature. Aiming at providing accurate representation, actual data from the existing facility is used to calibrate and validate the proposed model. Subsequently, the nonlinear model is linearized in order to conduct a linear model parameter study of the solar furnace model behavior. Finally, general constraint considerations are presented for formulating the MPC restrictions taking into account actual system thresholds.

2.1. Solar furnace description

Figure 1 illustrates the solar furnace SF60. This solar furnace system comprises a heliostat with a reflectivity efficiency of 95%, along with a parabolic collector possessing a reflecting surface area of 108 m² and a reflectivity of 95%. The collector redirects the radiation toward a focal area with a diameter of 22 cm, corresponding to an area of 0.038 m². A 4 m high turret surrounds the collector focus and serves as the test area. The turret is equipped with movable supports that allow the attachment of auxiliary devices based on the specific type of test being conducted.

In this work, the sample material under test is Silicon Carbide, measuring 50.4×50.3×5.7 mm³ in dimensions. The furnace shutter is composed of multiple slats, and its opening degree can be adjusted between 0% and 100% [4, 26].

Figure 1: Solar furnace SF60 located in the PSA facility. Courtesy of PSA.

The presented system model is obtained from the simplified energy balance proposed in [11]. The differential

Table 2

Model parameters of the SF60 solar furnace system.

Parameter	Description	Value-units
c_s	Specific heat	1142 J/kgK
m_s	Sample mass	0.025 kg
S_c	Collector surface	108 m ²
S_{f90}	Focus surface	0.038 m ²
S_p	Sample surface	0.0025 m ²
α_o	Maximum shutter angular aperture	50.8°
ρ_c	Collector reflectivity	0.9199
ρ_h	Heliostat reflectivity	0.9018
σ	Stephan–Boltzmann constant	5.67 · 10 ⁻⁸ W/(m ² K)

equation is designed as follows:

$$\frac{dT(t)}{dt} = f(T(t), I(t), T_a(t), u(t)), \quad (1)$$

for what the nonlinear function is

$$f(T(t), I(t), T_a(t), u(t)) = \frac{\rho_c \cdot \rho_h \cdot S_c}{S_{f90} \cdot \sin(\alpha_o)} \cdot \frac{S_p \cdot \alpha_a}{m_s \cdot c_s} \cdot I(t) \cdot \left(\sin(\alpha_o) - \sin \left[\left(1 - \frac{u(t)}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \right) - \frac{\alpha_e \cdot \sigma \cdot S_p}{m_s \cdot c_s} \cdot (T(t)^4 - T_a^4(t)) - \frac{\alpha_c \cdot S_p}{m_s \cdot c_s} \cdot (T(t) - T_a(t)). \quad (2)$$

The variables $T(t)$ [K] and $u(t)$ [%] are the sample temperature and shutter opening, representing the system output and input, respectively. The disturbance variables are the direct irradiance $I(t)$ [W/m²] and the ambient temperature $T_a(t)$ [K]. The model parameters description and its respective values are presented in Table 2. Notice that the proposed model in Eq. (2) considers parameters α_a , α_c , and α_e as a lumped-parameters representing the sample absorption capacity, the convection losses coefficient, and the sample emissivity. These parameters take into account the variations of the sample and the environmental conditions. Therefore, it is conventional that their values are not entirely known and may be a source of uncertainties in the model characterization. The identification and calibration of these parameters are detailed in the next section.

2.2. Model calibration and validation

For the purpose of obtaining a representative model, a parameter identification procedure is performed to approximate optimal values for α_a , α_c , and α_e in order to adequately represent the system dynamics.

In this context, a classical least-square optimization method is employed to identify the optimal values of parameters α_a , α_c , and α_e that minimize the following cost function

$$\min_{\alpha_a, \alpha_c, \alpha_e} J = \min \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^{k=N} (\hat{T}(k) - T(k))^2, \quad (3)$$

subject to model dynamics in discrete time, by applying the forward Euler method, and the maximum and minimum limits of each variable, such as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}(k+1) &= f(\hat{T}(k), I(k), T_a(k), u(k), \alpha_a, \alpha_c, \alpha_e), \\ \hat{T}(0) &= T(0), \\ \alpha_{a,min} &\leq \alpha_a \leq \alpha_{a,max}, \\ \alpha_{c,min} &\leq \alpha_c \leq \alpha_{c,max}, \\ \alpha_{e,min} &\leq \alpha_e \leq \alpha_{e,max}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

in which $\hat{T}(k)$ is the model temperature, $T(k)$, $I(k)$, $T_a(k)$, $u(k)$ are the actual data of the system and $k = 0$ is the initial sample time.

First, a calibration experiment was conducted on May 29, 2023, in which several step variations were done in the shutter aperture to reach the operating range for the sample material. The *fmincon* algorithm from the Matlab Optimization toolbox [27] is used to obtain the optimal value for parameters α_a , α_c , and α_e that minimizes Eq. (3). In this stage, the parameter limits are defined as 0.1, 10, and 0.1 for $\alpha_{a,min}$, $\alpha_{c,min}$, and $\alpha_{e,min}$, respectively, and 0.9, 80, and 1 for $\alpha_{a,max}$, $\alpha_{c,max}$, and $\alpha_{e,max}$, respectively. The limits are chosen based on the physical representation of the parameters used to describe the sample temperature and the experience of the researchers, being selected to align with the logical ones for this type of sample material [4].

Later, on May 31, 2023, the validation test was performed, repeating the same procedure of step changes for different meteorological and temperature conditions. Hence, with the data from the validated test, the optimal values for α_a , α_c , α_e are checked. Figure 2 depicts the validation results.

As a metric to evaluate the model validity, the R² index, the normalized Root Mean Squared Error (nRMSE), and the mean percentage error are obtained as 0.9171, 0.0561, and 4.93 %, demonstrating an acceptable result for developing model-based strategies. As can be evidenced from Fig. 2, the parameters are well-calibrated during the initial phase of the experiment, characterized by relatively low irradiance levels. However, as the irradiance increases and a second stage of the calibration experiment is conducted, the model exhibits greater deviations from the actual system data. Note that the main deviations are primarily observed in the model gain, as the identified parameters can properly capture the system dynamics at each operating point. As will be discussed further, direct irradiance has a more significant impact on the model gains than the time constant. This implies that when the system is subjected to varying levels of irradiance, the model gains may slightly deviate if a fixed lumped parameter is used in the nonlinear model.

Nonetheless, the optimal values obtained for α_a , α_c , and α_e are valid and representative when considering the entire experiment, as the error indices remain consistently low throughout the test. Thus, based on the achieved error indices, the identified parameters can be used for representing the model evolution without compromising the controllers' performance. Finally, Table 3 presents the identified optimal model parameters.

Figure 2: Validation results for the solar furnace SF60 model with a confidence interval of 95% (gray shadow).

Table 3

Model parameters of the SF60 solar furnace system identified by optimization method.

Parameter	Description	Value-units
α_a	Sample absorption capacity	0.5013
α_c	Convection losses coefficient	45.17 W/(m ² K)
α_e	Sample emissivity	0.5958

2.3. Model linearization and linear model analysis

Conducting a linear model parameter analysis can yield valuable insights into the system dynamics to achieve effective control of solar furnaces. Furthermore, a GPC and NGPC are developed for study and comparison matters, in which a linear model is necessary to obtain either the free or the forced responses and calculate the output prediction. Therefore, the presented nonlinear differential equation in Eq. (2) must be approximated in a specific operating point by obtaining a representative linearized model. Hence, the analysis is conducted considering the model gains and time constant to understand and investigate the effect of the nonlinearities in the solar furnace model.

Using the Taylor series truncated in the first term, and considering the deviation variables $\tilde{I}(t)$, $\tilde{T}(t)$, $\tilde{T}_a(t)$, $\tilde{u}(t)$ as $\tilde{I}(t) = I(t) - \bar{I}$, $\tilde{T}(t) = T(t) - \bar{T}$, $\tilde{T}_a(t) = T_a(t) - \bar{T}_a$, and $\tilde{u}(t) = u(t) - \bar{u}$, in which \bar{I} , \bar{T} , \bar{T}_a , and \bar{u} are the values of each variable in the quasi-stationary point of the system (since the irradiance slightly varies in time), one can obtain the following linearized model of Eq. (2)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\tilde{T}(t)}{dt} + (P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}^3) \cdot \tilde{T}(t) = & \\ \left(\sin \alpha_o - \sin \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \right) \cdot P1 \cdot \tilde{I}(t) & \\ + P1 \cdot \frac{\alpha_o}{100} \cdot \bar{I} \cdot \cos \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \cdot \tilde{u}(t) & \\ + (P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}_a^3) \cdot \tilde{T}_a(t), & \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

in which the auxiliary constants $P1$, $P2$, and $P3$ are $P1 = \frac{\rho_c \cdot \rho_h \cdot S_c}{S_{f90} \cdot \sin(\alpha_o)} \cdot \frac{S_s \cdot \alpha_a}{m_s \cdot c_s}$, $P2 = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot \sigma \cdot S_s}{m_s \cdot c_s}$, and $P3 = \frac{\alpha_e \cdot S_s}{m_s \cdot c_s}$.

The presented first-order linear model transfer functions can be used to formulate controllers by applying the Laplace

transform, which leads to the following equation in the frequency domain s

$$\tilde{T}(s) = \frac{K_I}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{I}(t) + \frac{K_{T_a}}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{T}_a(s) + \frac{K_u}{(\tau s + 1)} \tilde{u}(s), \quad (6)$$

assuming the model parameters as

$$\begin{aligned} K_I &= \frac{\left(\sin \alpha_o - \sin \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right] \right) \cdot P1}{\left(P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}^3 \right)}, \\ K_{T_a} &= \frac{\left(P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}_a^3 \right)}{\left(P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}^3 \right)}, \\ K_u &= \frac{P1 \cdot \frac{\alpha_o}{100} \cdot \bar{I} \cdot \cos \left[\left(1 - \frac{\bar{u}}{100} \right) \alpha_o \right]}{\left(P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}^3 \right)}, \\ \tau &= \frac{1}{\left(P3 + P2 \cdot 4 \cdot \bar{T}^3 \right)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The proposed model representation is very useful for studying the behavior of the system regarding the input gains and time constant. From Eq. (7), it can be observed that the linear model parameters are dependent on the \bar{I} , \bar{T} , \bar{T}_a , and \bar{u} . Therefore, considering a normal operation of the solar furnace, the linear model parameters analysis is investigated for a range of operational conditions in which the linear model is obtained. By assuming that the ambient temperature varies very slightly during the day, the analysis is conducted considering the variations of \bar{I} , \bar{T} , and \bar{u} solely. Hence, the operating conditions range is defined for $100 \text{ [W/m}^2\text{]} \leq \bar{I} \leq 1000 \text{ [W/m}^2\text{]}$, $330 \text{ [}^\circ\text{C]} \leq \bar{T} \leq 1100 \text{ [}^\circ\text{C]}$, and $0 \text{ [%]} \leq \bar{u} \leq 25 \text{ [%]}$. The selected range is chosen based on the security criteria of the experiment in which the sample temperature should not over-passes the defined limit. Consequently, the shutter aperture is also limited to the maximum threshold to avoid high-temperature levels.

Firstly, Fig. 3 details the variation of the K_u regarding the combination of the three variables \bar{I} , \bar{T} , and \bar{u} . One can observe that as the temperature decreases and the light incidence increases (which is directly affected by the shutter opening and direct solar irradiance), the gains associated with the input variable $u(t)$ also increase. Conversely, the gain relationship diminishes at higher sample temperatures, indicating a greater amount of energy needed to raise the sample temperature. This fact translates into larger amplitudes in the shutter aperture to make an increase of 1 °C of the sample temperature.

Regarding the irradiance gain, in Fig. 4, it can be noted that this parameter affects more the sample temperature for low ranges of temperature and higher shutter aperture as the K_I is higher for these operating conditions. Furthermore, in comparison to the K_u magnitudes, the value of K_I is notably lower, reaching up to 25 times less than the magnitudes of input gains. In this context, it must be noted that the effect of

Figure 3: Linear model parameters analysis of K_u gain. On the superior left graphic, \bar{T} is kept constant for 800 [W/m²]. On the superior right graphic, \bar{u} is kept constant in 15 [%]. On the inferior graphic, \bar{T} is constant in 600 [°C].

solar irradiance affects the control of the sample temperature mainly because it considerably changes the gains of the input K_u rather than the inherent variations that act as disturbances and directly impact the sample temperature since the value of K_I remains considerably low in comparison to K_u .

Finally, K_{T_a} and τ variations are observed in Fig. 5 in function of the sample temperature. It can be observed that these parameters vary almost linearly regarding the sample temperature, with the difference that the K_{T_a} range is considerably low, from 0.62 to 0.18, while the time constant varies largely from 134 s to 36 s.

When it comes to assessing closed-loop control performance, the variation in time constants poses a significant challenge. This is because a linear or poorly tuned controller may even exhibit satisfactory performance within a specific range of operations. However, its effectiveness deteriorates as the sample temperature deviates further from the intended operating condition. This matter strengthens the necessity of studying nonlinear controllers that accurately consider the nonlinear solar furnace model in its formulation.

Figure 4: Linear model parameter analysis of K_I gain.

2.4. Operational and process constraints

The solar furnaces are designed for thermal stress experiments. Therefore, strict thresholds are imposed for the variations in the sample temperature, such as gradient limits and maximum and minimum temperature bounds. Moreover, operational limits due to the mechanical conditions of

Figure 5: Linear model parameter analysis of K_{T_a} and τ .

equipment, namely, the shutter and the sensors, also impose diverse constraints that must be respected for the proper functioning of the facility. These limits are translated into restrictions for the MPC strategies both for the inputs and outputs.

Firstly, considering the sample used in this work, the Silicon Carbide, a gradient limit of 8 °C is necessary since this material can damage when submitted to abrupt temperature variations. Moreover, the thermocouple sensor used in the facility is directly embedded in the sample to homogeneously measure its temperature, and it can not exceed 1100 °C for the purpose of its integrity. Finally, the shutter velocity is mechanically limited to 8%/s, which it converts into the input variation limits, and the maximum shutter aperture is defined to 30%, which restrains the amount of irradiance and, thus, avoids damage to the thermocouple and to the sample itself.

3. MPC controllers formulation and analysis

Four different MPC strategies are presented in this section. Herein, the purpose is to study practical solutions that can be straightforwardly implemented in the existing solar furnace system. First, the GPC, NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC model prediction equations are presented. Then, the control optimization problems are formulated for the four control approaches. Subsequently, the control scheme is detailed, considering an offset-free method in the case that mismatch scenarios arise. Finally, a simulation scenario is run to evaluate the performance of the four MPC strategies.

Throughout this work, there is a gradual evolution of the proposed control solutions, focusing on enhancing closed-loop performance. Initially, the GPC controller relies on a linear model for output predictions, but its effectiveness reduces as the system strays from the linearized point. To address this limitation, the NGPC incorporates the nonlinear model into the free response term of the linear prediction equation. However, the forced response still fails to capture the full dynamics of the nonlinear system, potentially impacting the control performance. Consequently, an explicit NMPC approach is introduced, considering the complete nonlinearity of the system model. Finally, aiming to address the computational burden, the PNMPC is implemented, where the nonlinear model is linearized at each controller

sample time to obtain a linear prediction equation for the nonlinear model.

It is noteworthy that the computational cost of the MPC strategies is an important issue to be treated in practical applications. The MPC main idea is developed over the receding horizon concept, in which the constrained optimization problem is solved at each sample time for a defined prediction horizon. However, the entire obtained solution is never implemented, and only the first optimal control action is applied to the system. For the subsequent instants, the procedure is repeated, and again, only one control action is implemented. This aspect makes the computational burden increases significantly compared to the analytical solution since the entire constrained optimization step is necessarily repeated within each sample time. This concern associated with control performance is the focus of the next section.

3.1. GPC output prediction

The GPC outputs prediction is developed by employing the Controller Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (CARIMA) model. Considering a reasonable approximation of the nonlinear model Eq. (2) to the first-order linear model detailed in Eq. (6), the linear model representation can be expressed as

$$\Delta A(z^{-1})y(k) = B(z^{-1})\Delta u(k-1) + B_I(z^{-1})\Delta I(k-1) + B_{T_a}(z^{-1})\Delta T_a(k-1) + C(z^{-1})e(k), \quad (8)$$

in which k is the discretized time for a T_s sampling time, $y(k)$ is sample temperature variable ($y(k) = T(k)$), $\Delta u(k-1)$ is the shutter increments as manipulated variable, $\Delta I(k-1)$ and $\Delta T_a(k-1)$ are the irradiance and the temperature increments, $e(k)$ is a zero mean white noise, $A(z^{-1})$, $B(z^{-1})$, $B_I(z^{-1})$, $B_{T_a}(z^{-1})$, $C(z^{-1})$ are the polynomials coefficients defined for the backward shift operator z^{-1} , and $\Delta = 1 - z^{-1}$.

Considering Eq. (8) and following the formulation detailed in [28], the prediction of the system output can be obtained as

$$\hat{Y}_{GPC} = F_{GPC} + G_{GPC}\Delta u + G_{I,GPC}\Delta I + G_{T_a,GPC}\Delta T_a, \quad (9)$$

where \hat{Y}_{GPC} is the vector of the predicted sample temperature, that is,

$$\hat{Y}_{GPC} = [\hat{T}(k+1), \hat{T}(k+2), \dots, \hat{T}(k+N_p)]^\top, \quad (10)$$

in which N_p is the prediction horizon, and the F_{GPC} is the free response vector as the free evolution of the system resulting from the past input, output, and disturbances values. The matrix G_{GPC} is the forced response for the future inputs increments, and $G_{I,GPC}$, and $G_{T_a,GPC}$ are the disturbances response for the future predictions of the disturbances. Also, Δu , ΔI , and ΔT_a are the future increments of the inputs and disturbances, respectively, defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u &= [\Delta u(k), \Delta u(k+1), \dots, \Delta u(k+N_c)]^\top, \\ \Delta I &= [\Delta I(k), \Delta I(k+1), \dots, \Delta I(k+N_p)]^\top, \\ \Delta T_a &= [\Delta T_a(k), \Delta T_a(k+1), \dots, \Delta T_a(k+N_p)]^\top, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

for control horizon N_c , in which $\Delta u(k) = u(k) - u(k-1)$, $\Delta I(k) = I(k) - I(k-1)$ and $\Delta T_a(k) = T_a(k) - T_a(k-1)$.

In the presented form, the free response vector can be divided as

$$F_{GPC} = Qy_p + P_u\Delta u_p + P_I\Delta I_p + P_{T_a}\Delta T_{a_p}. \quad (12)$$

The free response of the system is the result of the past increments of the input Δu_p , and the disturbances ΔI_p and ΔT_{a_p} , associated to the matrices P_u , P_I , and P_{T_a} , respectively. Moreover, the free response F_{GPC} also depends on the free evolution of the system related to the matrix Q and the past inputs values y_p . Notice that for the chosen first-order linear model representation, only the last value of the input and disturbances $\Delta u(k-1)$, $\Delta I(k-1)$, and $\Delta T_a(k-1)$, and the current measure of the output $y(k) = T(k)$ are necessary to calculate the free response vector. For brevity, the construction of matrices for the free and forced response is not provided here. For more detailed information, please refer to the GPC formulation in [29, 30].

3.2. NGPC output prediction

As demonstrated previously, the GPC formulation requires a linear model description of a nonlinear system. In order to achieve a more accurate prediction, the free response of the system, which depends only on the past inputs, outputs, and disturbances values, can be obtained from the nonlinear model. In this solution, namely, NGPC, the output prediction equation is still linear since the forced term maintains the linear relation between the input and output. Therefore, the optimization problem can be formulated as a Quadratic-Programming (QP), which considerably reduces the computational costs of an explicit NMPC. From the theoretical point of view, this solution lacks rigorous proof of convergence since the superposition principle only holds for linear systems [19]. Nevertheless, the NMPC has proven its effectiveness in different practical scenarios, including applied in solar furnace systems [8, 19].

Therefore, the output prediction for the NGPC is obtained as follows

$$\hat{Y}_{NGPC} = F_{NGPC} + G_{GPC}\Delta u + G_{I,GPC}\Delta I + G_{T_a,GPC}\Delta T_a, \quad (13)$$

for what

$$F_{NGPC} = f(T(k), I(k-1), T_a(k-1), u(k-1)). \quad (14)$$

The function $f(T(k), I(k-1), T_a(k-1), u(k-1))$ is the discretized nonlinear model described in Eq. (2). Note that the measured values of the inputs and disturbances at $k-1$ and the current measured output $T(k)$ are kept constant along the prediction horizon to obtain the output values at each instant from $k+1$ to $k+N_p$ to construct F_{NGPC} . Similarly to the GPC, the current measured disturbances $T_a(k)$ and $I(k)$ are used for the future disturbance responses in ΔT_a and ΔI . For this prediction, when $N_c < N_p$, the last input action of the control horizon is kept constant until the end of the

prediction horizon, that is, $u(k + N_c + i) = u(k + N_c)$, for $i \in [1, N_p - N_c]$.

In summary, the free response F_{NGPC} is obtained as an evolution of the nonlinear system when the inputs and disturbances are considered constants along the predictions horizon. Moreover, notice that the forced matrices for the future inputs and disturbances predictions are strictly the same as the linear GPC formulation in Eq. (9).

3.3. NMPC output prediction

As the forced response of the NGPC controller remains computed from the approximated linearized model, the controller can still lose performance when applied to the actual nonlinear system. In this context, the NMPC strategy is presented to overcome linear model-based controllers since it uses the complete nonlinear model to predict future output values. The computation of the output prediction is straightforwardly obtained as

$$\hat{Y}_{NMPC} = f(T(k+i), I(k+i), T_a(k+i), u(k+i)), \quad (15)$$

in which $T_a(k+i)$ and $I(k+i)$ are the prediction of the disturbances, $u(k+i)$ are the optimal future control actions, and $T(k+i)$ is the future output values $\forall i \in [0, N_p]$. Similar to the NGPC strategy, when $N_c < N_p$, it is assumed the last input value, $u(k + N_c + i) = u(k + N_c)$.

The main concern of NMPC strategies revolves around determining the optimal control actions $u(k+i)$. Note that the current measured values of output $T(k)$, and the disturbances $T_a(k)$, and $I(k)$ are used in the prediction for $\hat{T}(k+i+1)$. Consequently, since NMPC involves formulating and solving optimization problems repeatedly in real-time to determine the optimal control actions, it can be computationally demanding, especially as the model involves cosine functions and terms to the four power as detailed in Eq. (2). This computational burden poses a challenge for implementing NMPC controllers in the actual solar furnaces application, where fast control decisions are required, and several constraints are imposed on the optimization problem.

3.4. PNMPC output prediction

Focusing on solving the computational burden of the NMPC strategy, the PNMPC framework is proposed. Moreover, considering that the GPC and NGPC do not adapt the system model to the actual operating point, the PNMPC can offer a more accurate prediction of the nonlinear system.

The PNMPC uses the nonlinear model of the solar furnace to calculate the free response in the same manner as the NGPC. However, the forced responses are calculated at each sampling time as the gradient of the outputs regarding the past input and disturbances. Hence, the resulting prediction equation is linear, and a simple QP can be formulated to compute the optimal future control increments. The predicted outputs computed by the PNMPC approach can be described as follows:

$$\hat{Y}_{PNMPC} = F_{PNMPC} + G_{PNMPC}\Delta u + G_{I,PNMPC}\Delta I + G_{T_a,PNMPC}\Delta T_a,$$

wherein F_{PNMPC} is calculated as the NGPC solution

$$F_{PNMPC} = f(T(k), I(k-1), T_a(k-1), u(k-1)), \quad (17)$$

and the forced response matrices are calculated as

$$G_{PNMPC} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta u(k|k)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta u(k+1|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|k)}{\partial \Delta u(k+1|k)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta u(k|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta u(k+1|k)} & \dots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta u(t+N_c-1|k)} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$G_{I,PNMPC} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k|k)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k+1|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k+1|k)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k+1|k)} & \dots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta I(k+N_p-1|k)} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$G_{T_a,PNMPC} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k|k)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+1|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k+1|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k+1|k)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k|k)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k+1|k)} & \dots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(k+N_p|k)}{\partial \Delta T_a(k+N_p-1|k)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

The forced response is calculated at each sample time of the PNMPC controller, and thus, considering that it is formulated over a nonlinear model, matrices G_{PNMPC} , $G_{I,PNMPC}$, and $G_{T_a,PNMPC}$ can change over time. Comprehensive detail of the PNMPC prediction equation can be reviewed in Plucenio et al. [24].

3.5. General control scheme and optimization problem

As presented in [29], the CARIMA model used in the GPC strategy accounts for the incremental form of the inputs and outputs in the free response F_{GPC} and an additional term $C(z^{-1})e(k)$ that considers the error between the model prediction and the plant outputs when unmeasured disturbances or model mismatch scenarios occur. However, for the NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC, although they include the incremental form of the inputs, the free response is calculated over an explicit nonlinear model considering the system's past outputs. Hence, when the model does not match the system dynamics, it generates a steady-state error in the closed loop.

In order to solve this issue, in this work, a solution for eliminating steady-state error is presented, which consists of including the prediction error in output prediction. Moreover, instead of using the actual past outputs of the system to calculate the model prediction, the own model outputs are fed back. Furthermore, a filter can be implemented in the prediction error to improve the controller's robustness. This solution is inspired by the works in [31] and [32], in which the GPC is evaluated as an optimal predictor plus a primary controller such as a Smith Predictor in a Dead Time Compensator (DTC) structures with a properly designed filter to improve the robustness properties.

Following this approach, the prediction equations for the NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{Y}_{NGPC} &= F_{NGPC} \Delta u + G_{I, GPC} \Delta I + \\ &\quad G_{T_a, GPC} \Delta T_a + Ie(k), \\ \hat{Y}_{NMPC} &= f(\hat{T}(k+i), I(k+i), T_a(k+i), u(k+i)) + Ie(k), \\ \hat{Y}_{PNMPC} &= F_{PNMPC} \Delta u + G_{I, PNMPC} \Delta I, \\ &\quad + G_{T_a, PNMPC} \Delta T_a + Ie(k),\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}F_{NGPC} &= F_{PNMPC} = \\ &f(\hat{T}(k), I(k-1), T_a(k-1), u(k-1)),\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

and \mathbf{I} is the unitary vector of $N_p \times 1$ dimension. For the prediction error, a robust filter $F_r(z^{-1})$ is employed such as

$$e(k) = F_r(z^{-1}) (T(k) - \hat{T}(k|k-1)). \quad (21)$$

As presented in [24] and also studied in [33], the choice of the $F_r(z^{-1})$ filter structure is crucial to increase the robustness of the PNMPC controller, similarly to the GPC strategy wherein this performance tuning is associated to the polynomial $C(z^{-1})$. Moreover, this method is strictly related to the approach reported in [31] and [32] for the prediction error in DTC structures that account for different filter forms depending on the systems and disturbances dynamics. The closed-loop control scheme proposed for the NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC is depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: MPC scheme for free steady-state error.

In particular, for the PNMPC, the presented solution is an alternative to the presented approaches in the literature that deal with model uncertainties. First, as presented in [24], the free response F_{PNMPC} is calculated using the system outputs, and the process feedback is employed using the integral of the filtered predicted error. This formulation minimizes but not eliminates the offset error completely. Secondly, in comparison to [33], although the mentioned control scheme in Fig. 6 does not present robustness stability, this method is

easier to tune since no modification in the optimization problem constraints or control tuning is required, and a simple low-pass filter can be employed to improve robustness. In the next section, numerical experiments expose the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme, using the solar furnace as a test bed system.

Lastly, considering the sample temperature increment constraints (see Section 2), it is important to consider that high-frequency disturbances can affect the temperature gradient faster than the control action. As a result, in the formulation of the optimization problem, for the first predicted instant, this issue may lead to infeasible solutions. Hence, it is proposed an auxiliary slack variable to the optimization problem to enable feasible solutions of the control optimization loop. This solution has been presented for constrained controllers with stability guarantees [34], in which high magnitude values are posed in the weight matrix associated with the slacks variables to force the use only when it is necessary.

Therefore, by using the presented prediction model and considering the solar furnace control objective and the actual system's constraints, the optimization problem is proposed as

$$\begin{aligned}\min_{\Delta u, \delta_s} J, \\ J = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_p} \left| \hat{T}(k+i) - y_{sp}(k+i) \right|_{\mathbf{Q}}^2 + \\ \sum_{j=0}^{j=N_c-1} |\Delta u(k+j)|_{\mathbf{R}}^2 + |\delta_s|_{\mathbf{S}}^2,\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

s.t.:

$$\begin{aligned}u_{min} \leq u(k+j) \leq u_{max} \quad \forall j \in [0, N_c - 1], \\ \Delta u_{min} \leq \Delta u(k+j) \leq \Delta u_{max} \quad \forall j \in [0, N_c - 1], \\ T_{min} \leq \hat{T}(k+i) \leq T_{max} \quad \forall i \in [1, N_p] \\ \Delta T_{min} \leq \Delta \hat{T}(k+i) + \delta_s \leq \Delta T_{max} \quad \forall i \in [1, N_p],\end{aligned}\quad (23)$$

and to the predicted output for the respective controller as depicted in Eq. (9) and Eq. (19). The input and outputs thresholds are defined as u_{min} , Δu_{min} , u_{max} , and Δu_{max} for the shutter maximum and minimum limits and T_{min} , ΔT_{min} , T_{max} , and ΔT_{max} for the temperature maximum and minimum limits, respectively. Also, matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are the tuning weight parameters to the reference tracking error, and the input increments and \mathbf{S} is the weight matrix of the slack variable δ_s .

To investigate the performance of each control strategy, in the next section, a trustworthy simulation is employed to control the solar furnace with the presented controllers.

3.6. Study of controllers' performance

In this section, the performance of different control formulations is investigated in controlling the nonlinear solar furnace system. To accomplish this, the four controllers (GPC, NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC) are utilized to control

the validated nonlinear model, as described in Section 2. For each controller, two identical conditions are applied. Firstly, artificial step changes are introduced as disturbances to assess the controller's ability to reject disturbances effectively. Secondly, a model mismatch is introduced by altering the identified constants of Table 3 by 20%. These conditions represent scenarios commonly encountered in practical solar furnace facilities, where the presence of strong disturbances and uncertainties in model parameters can impact the performance of the MPC strategies.

For the GPC and NGPC controllers, the linear model is obtained at the initial conditions of the simulated scenario, which are $\bar{T} = 732.9$ °C, $\bar{I} = 793.92$ W/m², $\bar{u} = 10$ %, and $\bar{T}_a = 16.13$ °C, achieving the following linear model constants: $K_I = 0.4943$ °C·m²/W, $K_u = 41.1658$ °C/%, $K_{T_a} = 0.272$ and $\tau = 61.15$ s. For the four strategies, the same tuning is imposed as $T_s = 5$ s, $\mathbf{Q} = 1 \cdot \text{diag}(N_p)$, $\mathbf{R} = 10^5 \cdot \text{diag}(N_c)$, and $\mathbf{S} = 10^5$, for $N_p = 50$ and $N_c = 20$. It is important to mention that the sample time and prediction horizon are chosen considering to achieve a closed-loop time constant of 20 s, in which $T_s = 5$ s is an acceptable design as the controller can predict $50 \times 5 = 250$ s ahead, beyond the system settling time $\approx 20 \times 4 = 200$ s and also achieve the recommended ratio $\tau/T_s = 4$ [35, 30].

In this simulation, the constraints of the inputs and outputs are defined as $u_{min} = 0$ %, $u_{max} = 50$ %/s, $\Delta u_{max} = -\Delta u_{min} = 8$ %/s, and $T_{min} = 330$ °C, $\Delta T_{max} = -\Delta T_{min} = 8$ °C/s, $T_{max} = 1100$ °C. Notice that the variable rate restrictions Δu are imposed exaggeratedly over the actual limits in order not to limit the controllers' performance and hence, evaluate each strategy considering the ability of purely dealing with system model nonlinearity. Finally, the robust filter imposed for the predicted error is chosen as $F_r(z^{-1}) = 0.1813/(z - 0.8187)$ to attenuate the noise at high frequencies in which a simple first-order low-pass filter can be used for these purposes [36].

The control optimization problem is formulated using the Matlab Toolbox YALMIP [37, 27], in which the Quadratic Programming (QP) solver is used for the GPC, NGPC, and PNMPC, and the *fmincon* solver is used to the NMPC. Also, since the predictions of the disturbance are not available, it is considered that the irradiance and the ambient temperature are constant along the prediction horizon.

Figure 7 presents the simulation scenario of the four control approaches. Notably, the performance is similar for all controllers, mainly regarding the ability to eliminate steady-state error. Nevertheless, important insights can be obtained from the slight differences in the control performances. First, the PNMPC and NMPC provide almost identical behavior, demonstrating that the PNMPC approach is a powerful technique for overcoming the nonlinear model dynamics by approximating it at each sample time. Secondly, it can be noted that all controllers respect the maximum temperature of $T_{max} = 1100$ °C without generating overshoot to achieve this temperature. Moreover, due to the better match of the nonlinear model to the plant model, it can be noted that the NMPC and PNMPC present better disturbance rejection

Table 4

Performance indices for comparison between GPC, NGPC, NMPC and PNMPC approaches.

	nSAE [-]	Processing Time [s]
GPC	1	0.1434
NGPC	0.9972	0.1442
PNMPC	0.9432	0.1717
NMPC	0.9225	3.4477

and less overshoot in the reference step changes than the GPC and NGPC. Finally, it can also be observed that the NGPC slightly improves the performance regarding the GPC since the nonlinear free response accounts for the nonlinear behavior of the plant. As the temperature gradients are within limits, the control optimization problem does not use the slack variables, which are kept at zero throughout the simulation.

Figure 7: Control performance comparison of GPC, NGPC, NMPC and PNMPC.

Concerning the computational burden of each strategy, the processing time to compute the solution of the optimization problem is computed. In addition, the normalized Sum of the Absolute Error (nSAE) index is calculated to evaluate numerically the MPC strategies, considering the normalization benchmark value the highest SAE among the strategies (worst case). The performance indices are summarized in Table 4.

As observed, it becomes evident that the NMPC strategy requires significantly more processing time than the other control strategies, taking over 20 times longer to compute a single control action. Although the NMPC exhibits better performance improvements in the nSAE index compared to the GPC and NGPC strategies, the substantial increase in the optimization solution complexity is a notable drawback when considering its practical application. The smallest error for PNMPC and NMPC is strictly related to the best matching of the controller model used for prediction, where the first uses a repetitive linearization of the nonlinear model, and the second uses the nonlinear model itself. In this regard, the PNMPC strategy presents the best balance between performance and computational cost. It achieves a low error index comparable to the NMPC approach while maintaining a computational complexity similar to the linear GPC

Table 5
PNMPC control tuning parameters.

Control Parameters	Values
T_s	5
N_p	50
N_c	20
Q	$1 \cdot \text{diag}(N_p)$
R	$10^5 \cdot \text{diag}(N_c)$
S	10^5
Δu_{max}	-8 %/s
Δu_{min}	8 %/s
u_{max}	25 %
u_{min}	0 %
T_{max}	1100 °C
T_{min}	330 °C
ΔT_{max}	8 °C/s
ΔT_{min}	-8 °C/s

controller. In general, the PNMPC achieves approximately a 6% reduction in the nSAE index compared to the GPC while keeping a processing time more than 20 times faster than the NMPC.

Based on the presented analysis of the simulation scenario, the PNMPC strategy has demonstrated superior compromise indices, making it a promising approach for controlling the solar furnace SF60 as discussed in the upcoming section. It is important to emphasize that the objective proposed in this work is to present a constrained nonlinear control strategy capable of addressing the primary concerns associated with practical issues in the solar furnace system. The analysis presented earlier further strengthens the outlook for implementing the PNMPC strategy, as it directly tackles nonlinear dynamics, input and output constraints, disturbances, and optimal control actions, all integrated into a unified solution.

4. Controlling the solar furnace SF60

In this section, the PNMPC is employed to control the actual SF60 located in the PSA facilities. The goal is to demonstrate and validate the effectiveness of the nonlinear control strategy in several different scenarios encountered in thermal stress experiments in the Silicon Carbide sample material. The parameters for the PNMPC were tuned based on the previously simulated results and considering actual thresholds for the sample material, as detailed in Table 5.

Notice that the constraints for the sample temperature and the shutter opening are applied according to the real limitations of the material and the equipment. Moreover, the robust filter of the predicted error is considered as $F_r(z^{-1}) = 0.7603/(z-0.2397)$ after preliminary tuning trials to achieve a faster response in correcting the model mismatch errors. For the experiments, the irradiance signal is filtered with the low-pass filter $F_l(z^{-1}) = 0.2592/(z-0.7408)$ to avoid high-frequency changes. Finally, the predictions of the irradiance and ambient temperature are considered constant in the control optimization problem, as this approach presented good performance in the simulation scenario.

4.1. Scenario 1 - Disturbance rejection experiment

The initial experiment took place on June 01, 2023, and focused on studying the practical challenges of the solar furnace plant concerning the performance of the PNMPC controller. Several significant factors were examined during this scenario. Firstly, the presence of passing clouds proved influential, emphasizing the importance of investigating the controller's ability to handle strong disturbances in the irradiance. Additionally, a communication failure occurred during the test, impacting the accurate reading of the shutter's actual position and subsequently affecting the controller's computations. Furthermore, intentional modifications were made to the parabolic focus. Based on the operators' experience, it is known that the turret heats up and deviates from its original position. This displacement leads to a shift in the sample position from the predetermined mirror focus, introducing unmeasured disturbances to the control system. Consequently, intentional manual modifications in the focus were made to examine how the PNMPC controllers would respond to these unmeasured disturbances.

In this scenario, reference step changes of 100 °C were performed in the sample temperature throughout the experiment. The closed-loop response obtained a time constant between 22.0 and 24.6 for the first part of the test when the irradiance varied smoothly, which is similar to the one designed in the simulation tests. Figure 8 details the experiment results. It is noteworthy that the PNMPC strategy effectively controlled the sample temperature with no steady-state error, even when strong disturbances occurred. The applied tuning was adequate to generate a fast rise time in reference changes with acceptable overshoot and appropriate disturbance compensations. Regarding the unmeasured disturbance, the controller responded adequately, however, since the shutter opening was limited to 25%, the control action saturated, and hence it could not overcome the focus-changing effect. Nevertheless, it can be observed that the PNMPC could respond satisfactorily to the unmeasured disturbance and properly deal with natural focus displacement when it occurred in the experiment test.

Concerning the control constraints, the PNMPC respected all the system thresholds for the input and output, as seen in Figs. 8 and 9. Notice that the temperature gradient only surpassed the limits when manual interference was conducted in the sample focus position, which the PNMPC could not manage in this situation. Also, it can be observed the effect of the slack variables in Fig. 9 regarding the cost function in Eq. (22), which is used only when the temperature gradient is surpassed to provide feasible solutions to the control optimization problem.

4.2. Scenario 2 - Large step changes

For the second scenario on June 05, 2023, reference changes of 200 °C were conducted. After evaluating the results of the first experiment and considering higher magnitudes on the step change, the weigh matrix R was adjusted to $5 \cdot 10^5$ in order to avoid high overshoot. Figure 10 and 11 depicts the PNMPC performance.

Figure 8: PNMPC performance controlling the solar furnace SF60 on June 01, 2023.

Figure 10: PNMPC performance controlling the solar furnace SF60 on June 05, 2023.

Figure 9: Gradient of the shutter opening and sample temperature on June 01, 2023.

Figure 11: Gradient of the shutter opening and sample temperature on June 05, 2023.

As a first analysis, it can be noted the effect of the nonlinear behavior of the system. Notice that a small overshoot occurred in the first step change. On the other hand, this behavior diminished as the temperature rose, which corresponds to the same results encountered in Section 2 for the linear model parameter analysis of the input gain related to the temperature operating point. Moreover, smooth variations in solar irradiance affected the system, which made the control signal behaves very steadily. As commented in the previous section, the natural heating of the turret occurred during the experiment, which led the sample to deviate from the original parabolic focus. The PNMPC could manage this unmeasured disturbance straightforwardly, and it could not be noticed in the experiment until the intervention of the operator to readjust the sample position. This intervention can be seen highlighted in Fig. 10 on two occasions. As a result, this situation demonstrates the effectiveness of the controller in dealing with unmeasured disturbances without generating steady-state errors.

The presented results in Fig. 10 highlight the controller's performance in the reference tracking scenario since the low variations in the disturbance present a quasi-stationary behavior. Throughout the entire experiment, the attained closed-loop time constant remains consistently similar, ranging from 24.6 to 31.4 s. This indicates a slower response compared to the design in the simulation from Section 3, which is expected due to the large input weight matrix used in this test.

From Fig. 11, it can be noted the effect of the tuning adjustment in this test, wherein lower variations of the shutter opening occurred. Moreover, similarly to the test in the first scenario, the PNMPC was able to respect the input and output thresholds, mainly regarding the temperature gradients, which is the most important limits that must be respected in thermal stress experiments. The few points that surpassed the limits are caused by noises on the sample temperature measurement, which is evident since these gradients are only one point in the graphic in a decreasing trend of temperature that does not correspond with reality.

4.3. Results highlights

Focusing on studying the outcomes of the PNMPC strategy, it is possible to analyze the main accomplishments of the real-plant results regarding the objectives of this work. First, the PNMPC has important features to address the nonlinear dynamics of the solar furnace. As seen in Figs. 8 and 10, the controller is capable of controlling the system in a large spectrum of operating conditions, mainly for reference tracking both in low and high sample temperatures.

Secondly, the proposed control scheme for the PNMPC can address the steady-state error when model mismatch and unmeasured disturbances occur. This subject is studied in simulation trials, as detailed in Section 3, and proved in an actual experiment when the turret deviates from the parabolic collector focus, evidenced in the slight variations of the temperature as indicated in Fig 10.

Finally, as observed in Figs. 9 and 11, the constrained nonlinear controller attends the system threshold specifications, keeping the operational and security requirements within their limits, both for the inputs and outputs. This fact brings important guarantees to thermal stress experiments since the sample material can follow its thermal specifications throughout the test.

The presented results are outstanding regarding the state of the art of automatic control in a solar furnace system. Besides the contribution in [19], the solutions of constrained nonlinear control have not yet been addressed in the literature. In addition, this work makes advances regarding the solution presented in [19] since the solar furnace temperature is controlled entirely with the nonlinear strategy, and no switching algorithm is required.

5. Conclusions

The present work proposes a constrained nonlinear controller for solar furnace systems. First, calibration and validation experiments are conducted in the existing solar furnace SF60 (PSA, Almería, Spain) to obtain trustworthy models to develop model-based strategies. After studying the linear model parameter analysis regarding the system operating point, four different MPC strategies are investigated regarding the control performance and computational burden. The GPC, NGPC, NMPC, and PNMPC are proposed following a pertinent evolution on the control formulation basis in order to meet the performance requirements related to the nonlinear dynamic, disturbances, system constraints, optimal control action, and robustness. Based on the simulation results, the PNMPC presents the best compromise between performance and computational cost.

Hence, the PNMPC strategy is applied to control the existing SF60 system. Considering the proposed performance criteria, the PNMPC is capable of accomplishing the proposed requirements with concerns to dealing with nonlinear dynamics, disturbances compensation, constraints, and robustness regarding unmeasured disturbances. The outcomes have presented important contributions to improving the reliability and performance of thermal stress trials in solar furnaces. In addition, the nonlinear control comparison brings interesting insights into nonlinear control studies regarding practical implementation in constrained and disturbed nonlinear systems.

In future studies, there is a focus on addressing real-time adaptations of the model parameters, as they are the primary source of uncertainties that have the potential to impact the performance of the controller. In addition, enlarging the inputs threshold should be studied in order to improve disturbances rejection, mainly concerning the irradiance variations. It is also essential to investigate temperature profile tests when implementing the nonlinear controller, particularly regarding ramp tracking, as this could lead to velocity errors and modeling the wind effect over the heliostat.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work has been partially financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science [grant numbers PID2020-112709RB-C21]. Igor M. L. Pataro acknowledges the financial support of the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq, Brazil) under grant 201143/2019 – 4. The authors thank José Rodríguez, José Galindo, and Lidia Roca for the technical and operational support of the experiments in the Plataforma Solar de Almería, CIEMAT, Spain.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Igor M. L. Pataro: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review, and editing, Visualization.. **Juan D. Gil:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review, and editing, Visualization.. **José L. Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.. **Manuel Berenguel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.. **Inmaculada Cañadas:** Technical support, Facility operation, Writing - review, Visualization..

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